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Statistical Analysis of Fish Species Variation in Relation to Seasons and Environmental Factors in Urasì Okija Town, Ihiala Local Government, Anambra State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The fish sample collected from the locations of the study area was statistically analyzed to distinguish species composition, abundance, richness and diversity in relation to change in seasons and other environmental factors. Among the eight (8) order of specie shown in the results, the most abundant of species was *Clarias gariepinus* with percentage of 90, 9.5 %, followed by *polypterus-senegalus* 74, 8.0 %. *Districhodus rostratus* (19) is the least species which recorded percentage composition of 2.0 %. There is higher abundance of fish species occurrence in dry season 50.0 % while in the wet season revealed 49.4 %. The result revealed higher abundance of fish species in the month of June 13.6% 2023 and lowest in the month of December (4.5%) 2022. Fishes are one of the most important group of vertebrates serving as food for human. These revealed results contribute to conservative potentials of fish species in the environs of Urasì. Fishes possess a great economic, nutritional, medicinal, industrial, aesthetic and religious values as well as providing employment for millions of people in the world. Fishes contribute to food security in the study area, providing a valuable supplement for diversified and nutritious diets.

Keywords: Fish Sample, *Districhodus rostratus*, Climate Change, species composition food security and *Clarias gariepinus*

1. INTRODUCTION

Fish are aquatic, craniate, fin, and limbless gill-bearing animals that lack limbs with digits. (Gland 2021). Included in this definition are the living hagfish, lampreys, and cartilaginous and bony fish as well as various extinct related groups (Gland, 2021). Approximately 95% of living fish species are ray-finned fish, belonging to the Class Actinopterygii, with around 99% of those being teleosts (Awiti, 2011). The earliest organisms that can be classified as fish were soft-bodied chordates that first appeared during the Cambrian period (Vander, 2011). Although they lacked a true spine, they possessed notochords which allowed them to be more agile than their invertebrate counterparts (David, 2010). Fish would continue to evolve through the Paleozoic era, diversifying into a wide variety of forms. Many fish of the Paleozoic developed external armour that protected them from predators. The first fish with jaws appeared in the Silurian period, after which many (such as sharks) became formidable marine predators rather than just the prey of arthropods. Most fish are ectothermic ("cold-blooded"), allowing their body temperatures to vary as ambient temperatures change, though some of the large active swimmers like white shark and tuna can hold a higher core temperature. Fish can acoustically communicate with each other, most often in the context of feeding, aggression or courtship (Andersirk *et al.*, 2005). Fish are abundant in most bodies of water. They can be found in nearly all aquatic environments, from high mountain Rviers (e.g., char and gudgeon) to

the abyssal and even hadal depths of the deepest oceans (e.g., cusk-eels and snailfish), although no species has yet been documented in the deepest 25% of the ocean. With 34,300 described species, fish exhibit greater species diversity than any other group of vertebrates (Byers, 2005).

Fish are an important resource for humans worldwide, especially as food (David, 2010). Commercial and subsistence fishers hunt fish in wild fisheries or farm them in ponds or in cages in the ocean (in aquaculture). They are also caught by recreational fishers, kept as pets, raised by fishkeepers, and exhibited in public aquaria. Fish have had a role in culture through the ages, serving as deities, religious symbols, and as the subjects of art, books and movies. Tetrapods (amphibians, reptiles, birds and mammals) emerged within lobe-finned fishes, so cladistically they are fish as well. However, traditionally fish (pisces or ichthyces) are rendered paraphyletic by excluding the tetrapods, and are therefore not considered a formal taxonomic grouping in systematic biology, unless it is used in the cladistic sense, including tetrapods, although usually "vertebrate" is preferred and used for this purpose (fish plus tetrapods) instead (Byers, 2005). Furthermore, cetaceans, although mammals, have often been considered fish by various cultures and time periods (Mekonnen et al., 2016) are able to react to environmental changes quickly (Miller, 2022).

2. Study Area

The study area lies within the tropical rain forest zone on the coordinates ranging latitudes $05^{\circ} 51'00''$ N to $05^{\circ} 57'00''$ N and longitude $06^{\circ} 47'00''$ E to $06^{\circ} 51'00''$ E (Fig 1). The sample locations are situated in Isieke village Okija town of Ihiala Local Government of Anambra State, Nigeria. The typical tropical climate of the area is governed by the northeastern and southwestern winds which commonly influence the climate of Nigeria (Ibemenuga et al., 2017). There are two main seasons, the rainy season (April to September) and dry season (October to March) prominent in the study area.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Fish Sampling and Identification

Fish was collected fortnightly from each sampling station site for a period of twelve months with the help of fisherman. Different fishing gears include cast net, gill net, clap net, and hook net were used during this study collection took place in the morning, and were transported to the Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University laboratory in ice-cold bucket in order to prevent fish spoilage. The fish samples were identified in the laboratory with the help of Professor Nwosu from genus to species level using dorsal and anal fin counts, gill rakers counts, body shape, size and shape of caudal fin anal papillae fish were identified and sorted out into different species.

3.2 Statistical Analysis

The means, range percentages and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) at probability level of $P < 0.05$ of the data generated were determining using SPSS (V.19 by IBM corporation, Washington, USA) was used for graphically illustration. The community structure (margalef species diversity, Shannon-wiener index species evenness) was analyzed using (Donkan multiple range test) between groups.

3.3 Experimental Design

The experimental design used in completely randomized design.

Faunal Similarity of Study Station

Bellinger's coefficient was computed to evaluate faunal similarity between sampling stations.

$$\text{Bellingers coefficient} = \frac{(p - q)^2}{p + q}$$

Where

P = number of occasions in which the taxon occurs in one station than the others.

q = number of occasion where reverse in the case

Percentage Relative Abundance

The total number of each fish group was determined at each study station using the formula

$$\text{Percentage relative composition} = \frac{a}{b} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Where a = number of individuals recorded

b = total number of individuals record of all species in the station

Fish Diversity and Dominance

i. Magalets diversity index for species richness (d) wsa calculated thus:

$$D = \frac{S - 1}{\text{Log}N}$$

ii. Shannon weiner (H) was determined as follows

$$H = \frac{N \log N - \sum f_i \log f_i}{N}$$

iii. Evenness (E) was computed as follows

$$E = \frac{H}{H_{Max}}$$

iv. Dominance was calculated thus:

$$C = \left(\sum \frac{n_i}{N} \right)^2$$

Where n_i = number of individuals belonging to each species.

N = total number of individuals of all species.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

4.1 Fishes Species Occurrence, Composition, Distribution and Abundance

The result shows that eight (8) orders of fish species (*Osteoglossiforms*, *Anabantiforms*, *Cyprinodontiforms*, *Characiforms*, *Perciforms*, *Cichliform*, *Polyteriforms* and *silniform* were recorded in Table 1). These eight order were composed of fourteen (14) family (*mormyridae*, *Arapimidae*, *Anabatidaae*, *Aplocheiidae*, *Alestidae*, *Cichlidae*, *Polyperidae*, *Claridae*,

Malapteruridae, Mocholcidae) and twenty-four (24) sp Vecies and nine hundred and forty-eight (948) individuals. The order *Cichliform* (223) had the highest percentage species composition of (23.5 %) followed by *silniform*, 199, (21.0 %) and *Characiforms* 167, (17.1 %) followed by *Osteoglossiforms* 128, 13.6 %. *Anabantiforms* and *cyprinodontoforms* was the lest (26) with the percentage (2.7 %).

The most abundance family is *Cichlidae* (223) with the percentage composition of (23.5 %) followed by *Channidae* (109) with the percentage of (11.8 %) and were represented by only the (3) species. The least family was *Distichodontidis* (19) with a percentage composition of (2.0 %) and were represented by only one species. The most abundant of species was *Clarias gariepinus* (90, 9.5 %) followed by *polypterus-senegalus* (74, 8.0 %), *Districhodus rostratus* (19) the least species recorded with percentage composition (2.0 %).

Table 1: Composition and abundance of fish species in Urası River July 2022 – June 2023

TAXA				
Order	Family	Species	Total number of collected	% of total
<i>Osteoglossi-Forms</i>			128	13.6
	<i>Mormyridae</i>		99	10.5
		<i>Mormyrus-Rume</i>	45	4.8
		<i>Petrocephalus-borei</i>	29	3.1
		<i>Mormyrops-Anguilloides</i>	25	2.6
	<i>Arapaimidae (osteoglossidae)</i>		29	3.1
		<i>Heterotisi-iniloticus</i>	29	3.1
<i>Anabanti-Forms</i>			26	2.7
	<i>Anabantidae</i>		26	2.7
		<i>Ctenopoma-Kings leyar</i>	26	2.7
<i>Cyprinodon-Tiforms</i>			26	2.7
	<i>Aplocheiidae</i>		26	2.7
		<i>Epiplatys-fasciatus</i>	26	2.7
<i>Anabanti-Forms</i>			26	2.7
<i>Characiformes</i>			167	17.1
	<i>Alestidae (Characidae)</i>		89	8.9
		<i>Hydrocynus Forkali</i>	34	3.6
		<i>Hydrocynus Vittatus</i>	23	2.4
		<i>Brycinuleucicus</i>	28	2.9
	<i>Citharinidae</i>		36	3.8
		<i>Citharinidae-citharinus</i>	36	3.8
	<i>Distichodontidas</i>		19	2.0
		<i>Distichodus-rostratus</i>	19	2.0
	<i>Hepsetidae</i>		23	2.4

		<i>Parachanna- Obscura</i>	30	3.2
		<i>Parachanna- Africana</i>	34	3.6
		<i>Channachanna</i>	45	4.8
<i>Cichliformes</i>			223	23.5
	<i>Cichlidae</i>		223	23.5
		<i>Tilapia zilli</i>	41	4.3
		<i>Tilapia maria</i>	68	7.2
		<i>Sarotherodon- Galilus</i>	63	6.5
		<i>Oreochromis- miloticus</i>	51	5.4
<i>Polyteriformes</i>			74	8.0
	<i>Polypteridae</i>		74	8.0
		<i>Polypterus- senegalus</i>	74	8.0
<i>Siluriformes</i>			199	21.0
	<i>Clariidae</i>		90	9.5
		<i>Clarias- gsariepinus</i>	90	9.5
	<i>Malapteruridae</i>		34	3.6
		<i>Malapterurus- electricus</i>	34	3.6
	<i>Mochockidae</i>		75	7.9
		<i>Synodontis- Omias</i>	51	5.4
		<i>Synodontis- Sorex</i>	24	2.5
	TOTAL		948	100.1

Table 2: Variation of Fish in Urasi River in relation to months July-June 2022-2023

TAXA			Month											
Order	Family	Species	July	Aug	Sept.	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	April	May	June
Osteoglossi formes	Mormyridae		4(4.4)	6(6.7)	4(4.4)	4(8.9)	1(2.2)	4(8.9)	7(15.6)	5(11.1)	6(11.1)	4(8.9)	4(8.9)	4(8.9)
		<i>Mormyrus-Rume</i>	4(4.4)	6(6.7)	4(4.4)	4(8.9)	0(0.0)	4(8.9)	7(15.6)	6(11.1)	5(11.1)	4(8.9)	4(8.9)	4(8.9)
			2(4.4)	3(6.7)	2(4.4)	4(8.9)	1(2.2)	4(8.9)	7(15.6)	5(11.1)	5(11.1)	4(8.9)	4(8.9)	4(8.9)
			0(0.0)	3(10.3)	2(6.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(10.3)	5(17.2)	4(13.8)	4(13.8)	2(6.9)	4(13.8)	2(6.9)
			2(8.0)	0(0.0)	1(4.0)	1(4.0)	1(4.0)	0(0.0)	6(24.0)	2(8.0)	6(24.0)	0(0.0)	3(12.0)	3(12.0)
			2(6.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(10.3)	0(0.0)	6(24.0)	4(13.8)	7(24.1)	4(13.8)	0(0.0)	3(10.3)
			2(6.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(10.3)	0(0.0)	6(24.0)	4(13.8)	7(24.1)	4(13.8)	0(0.0)	3(10.3)
			3(3.0)	3(11.5)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	6(24.0)	0(0.0)	8(30.8)	3(1.5)	0(0.0)	3(11.5)
			3(15.5)	3(11.5)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	6(24.0)	0(0.0)	8(30.8)	3(1.5)	0(0.0)	3(11.5)
			3(11.5)	3(11.5)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	6(24.0)	0(0.0)	8(30.8)	3(1.5)	0(0.0)	3(11.5)
Cyprinodon-tiforms			1(4.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	2(6.0)	0(0.0)	5(2.0)	6(24.0)	5(20.5)	1(4.0)	2(8.0)	3(16.0)
			1(4.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	2(6.0)	0(0.0)	5(2.0)	6(24.0)	5(20.5)	1(4.0)	2(8.0)	3(16.0)
characiformes			1(4.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	2(8.0)	0(0.0)	5(2.0)	6(24.0)	5(20.5)	1(4.0)	2(8.0)	4(16.0)
			7(34.9)	8(26.9)	9(28.4)	13(43.4)	10(36.0)	10(40.8)	27(90.4)	15(56.2)	21(74.9)	17(66.9)	12(25.4)	14(40.1)
			4(26.6)	4(15.8)	5(15.4)	4(12.4)	4(11.9)	5(14.4)	13(35.0)	9(32.5)	15(56.2)	7(20.1)	9(25.4)	6(20.1)
			0(0.0)	0(0.0)	4(11.8)	3(8.8)	3(8.8)	3(8.8)	6(17.0)	3(8.8)	3(8.8)	4(11.8)	3(8.3)	2(5.9)
			3(13.0)	2(8.7)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	4(17.4)	3(13.0)	6(26.0)	0(0.0)	3(8.3)	2(7.1)
			1(3.6)	2(7.1)	1(3.6)	1(3.6)	1(3.6)	2(5.6)	3(10.8)	3(10.7)	6(21.4)	3(8.3)	3(8.3)	2(7.1)
			3(8.3)	4(11.1)	0(0.0)	4(11.1)	3(8.3)	4(11.1)	6(16.7)	3(8.3)	6(16.7)	3(8.3)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
			3(8.3)	4(11.1)	0(0.0)	4(11.1)	3(8.3)	4(11.1)	6(16.7)	3(8.3)	6(16.7)	3(8.3)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
			0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	1(5.3)	3(15.8)	1(5.3)	5(26.3)	3(15.8)	0(0.0)	4(21.1)	0(0.0)	2(10.5)
			0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	1(5.3)	3(15.8)	1(5.3)	5(26.3)	3(15.8)	0(0.0)	4(21.1)	0(0.0)	2(10.5)
		0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(13.0)	4(17.4)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(13.0)	0(0.0)	2(8.7)	4(17.14)	3(13.0)	4(17.4)	
		0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(13.0)	4(17.4)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(13.0)	0(0.0)	2(8.7)	4(17.14)	3(13.0)	4(17.4)	
Perciformes			10(25.1)	5(11.1)	4(12.1)	12(37.6)	19(51.7)	6(13.3)	14(40.7)	7(19.1)	8(27.7)	12(30.7)	1(2.98)	18(50.3)
			10(25.1)	5(11.1)	4(12.1)	12(37.6)	19(51.7)	6(13.3)	14(40.7)	7(19.1)	8(27.7)	12(30.7)	1(2.98)	18(50.3)

	<i>Parachanna-Obseur</i>	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	1(3.3)	6(20.0)	4(13.33)	0(0.0)	6(20.0)	1(3.3)	3(10.0)	3(10.0)	08(08.0)	6(20.0)	
	<i>Parachanna-Africana</i>	4(11.8)	0(0.0)	3(8.8)	6(17.6)	7(20.6)	0(0.0)	4(11.8)	4(11.4)	3(8.8)	4(11.8)	1(2.9)	5(14.7)	
	<i>Channachanna</i>	6(13.3)	5(1.1)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	8(17.8)	6(13.3)	4(8.9)	2(4.4)	2(8.9)	5(8.9)	0(0.0)	7(15.6)	
Cichliformes	<i>Cichlidae</i>		16(25.74)	24	18(45.5)	19	15(26.4)	15	13(27.6)	14(25.8)	19(36.2)	22(39.9)	19(44.0)	29(52.8)
			16(25.74)	24	18(5.5)	19(31.6)	15	15(26.4)	13(27.6)	14(25.8)	19(36.2)	22(39.9)	19(44.0)	29(52.8)
		<i>Tilapia zilli</i>	1(2.44)	5(11.1)	6(14.6)	0(0.0)	1(2.4)	1(2.4)	6(16.6)	3(7.3)	4(9.8)	4(9.8)	3(7.3)	7(17.1)
		<i>Tilapia mariae</i>	5(7.4)	9(13.2)	4(5.9)	7(11.1)	7(10.3)	4(5.9)	5(7.4)	3(7.3)	4(9.8)	6(8.8)	5(7.4)	9(13.2)
		<i>Sarotherodon-Galilus</i>	10(15.9)	4(6.3)	5(5.9)	6(9.5)	7(11.1)	4(6.3)	0(0.0)	4(7.8)	4(5.9)	6(9.5)	6(19.5)	8(12.7)
		<i>Oreochromis-miloticus</i>	0(0.0)	6(11.8)	3(5.9)	6(11.8)	0(0.0)	6(11.8)	2(3.9)	4(7.8)	3(4.8)	6(11.8)	5(9.8)	5(9.8)
				2(2.7)	5(6.6)	7(7.5)	5(6.6)	15(20.3)	5(6.6)	3(4.1)	4(7.8)	8(15.7)	6(8.1)	2(2.7)
Polyteriformes	<i>Polypteridae</i>		2(2.7)	5(6.6)	7(7.5)	5(6.6)	15(20.3)	5(6.6)	3(4.1)	4(7.8)	2(2.7)	6(8.1)	2(12.7)	18(24.3)
		<i>Polypterus-senegalus</i>	2(2.7)	5(6.6)	7(7.5)	5(6.6)	15(20.3)	5(6.6)	3(4.1)	4(7.8)	2(2.7)	6(8.1)	2(2.7)	18(24.3)
			15	0	26	14	33	0(0.0)	12	11(29.3)	2(2.7)	11(26.5)	18(24.3)	26(71.3)
siluriformes	<i>Clariidae</i>		7(7.8)	0(0.0)	15(1.7)	7(7.8)	20(22.2)	0(0.0)	3(3.3)	3(3.3)	30(42.1)	0(0.0)	10(11.1)	3(0.3)
		<i>Clarias-gariepinus</i>	7(7.8)	0(0.0)	15(1.7)	7(7.8)	20(22.2)	0(0.0)	3(3.3)	3(3.3)	22(24.4)	0(0.0)	10(11.1)	3(0.3)
	<i>Malapteruridae</i>		4(11.8)	0(0.0)	2(5.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	2(5.9)	6(17.7)	22(24.4)	5(14.7)	3(8.8)	3(24.4)
		<i>Malapterurus-electricus</i>	4(11.8)	0(0.0)	2(5.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	2(5.9)	6(17.7)	2(5.9)	5(14.7)	3(8.8)	10(24.4)
	<i>Mocholcidae</i>		0(0.0)	0(0.0)	9(24.3)	7(13.7)	13(32.1)	0(0.0)	7(18.1)	2(8.3)	2(5.9)	6(11.8)	5(20.8)	20(46.6)
		<i>Synodontis-Omias</i>	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	6(11.8)	7(13.7)	10(19.0)	0(0.0)	5(9.8)	0(0.0)	6(1.8)	6(11.8)	0(0.0)	14(21.6)
<i>Synodontis-Sorex</i>		0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(12.5)	0(0.0)	3(12.5)	0(0.0)	2(8.3)	2(8.3)	3(5.9)	0(0.0)	5(20.8)	6(25.0)	
	TOTAL	56(100)	51(100)	68(100)	68(100)	99(100)	43(100)	104(100)	72(100)	117(100)	83(100)	65(100)	129(100)	
		5.9 %	5.4 %	7.2 %	7.2 %	10.4 %	4.5 %	10.9 %	7.6 %	12.3 %	8.8 %	6.9 %	13.6 %	

4.2 Fish species variation in relation to month

The result from the study revealed that higher abundance of fish species occurred in the month of June (13.6 %) followed by March (12.3 %) followed again by January (10.9 %), the result from the studies revealed that lower abundance of fish species occurred in the month of December (4.5 %), followed by August 5.4 % followed again by September 7.2 % and followed again by May (6.9 %). Therefore, the result shows that the higher abundance occurred in the month of June 13.6 % 2023 and was lowest in the month of December (4.5 %) 2022 (Table 2).

Table 3: Variation of Fish in Urasi River in relation to stations July-June 2022-2023

TAXA		Station				
Order	Family	Species	A	B	C	
Osteoglossi-Forms			40(128.2)	49(148.3)	39(123.5)	
		<i>Mormyridae</i>	27(83.4)	39(113.8)	33(102.8)	
		<i>Mormyrus-Rume</i>	12(26.7)	20(44.4)	13(28.9)	
		<i>Petrocephalus-borei</i>	6(20.77)	12(41.4)	11(37.9)	
		<i>Mormyrops-Anguilloides</i>	9(36.0)	7(28.0)	9(36.0)	
		<i>Arapaimidae (osteoglossidae)</i>	13(4.8)	10(34.5)	6(20.7)	
		<i>Heterotisi-Iniloticus</i>	13(44.8)	10(34.5)	6(20.7)	
	Anabanti-Forms			9(34.6)	11(42.3)	6(20.7)
			<i>Anabantidae</i>	9(34.6)	11(42.3)	6(20.7)
			<i>Ctenopoma-Kings leyar</i>	9(34.6)	11(42.3)	6(20.7)
Cyprinodon-Tiforms			10(38.5)	3(11.5)	13(50.0)	
		<i>Aplocheiidae</i>	10(38.5)	3(11.5)	13(50.0)	
		<i>Epiplatysbi-Fasciatus</i>	10(38.5)	3(11.5)	13(50.0)	
Characiformes			53(2011.2)	64(226.4)	46(172.5)	
		<i>Alestidae (Characidae)</i>	23(80.7)	36(123.6)	26(95.7)	
		<i>Hydrocynus Forkali</i>	11(32.4)	14(41.2)	9(26.5)	
		<i>Hydrocynus Vittatus</i>	7(30.4)	5(21.7)	11(47.8)	
		<i>Brycinuleucicus</i>	5(17.9)	17(60.7)	6(21.4)	
		<i>Citharinidae</i>	11(30.6)	15(41.7)	10(27.8)	

		<i>Citharimus-citharinus</i>	11(30.6)	15(41.7)	10(27.8)	
	<i>Distichodontidas</i>		8(42.1)	5(26.3)	6(31.6)	
		<i>Distichodus-Rostratus</i>	8(42.1)	5(26.3)	6(31.6)	
	<i>Hepsetidae</i>		11(47.8)	8(34.8)	4(17.4)	
Perciformes		<i>Hepsetusodoe</i>	11(47.8)	8(34.8)	4(17.4)	
	<i>Channidae</i>		55(146.6)	29(83.5)	31(87.6)	
			55(146.6)	29(83.5)	31(87.6)	
		<i>Parachanna-Obscura</i>	9(30.0)	10(33.3)	11(36.7)	
	<i>Parachanna-africana</i>	20(58.8)	11(17.8)	9(26.6)		
		<i>Channachanna</i>	26(57.8)	8(17.8)	11(24.4)	
Cichliformes	<i>Cichlidae</i>		64(114.8)	111(198.5)	48(86.8)	
			64(114.8)	111(198.5)	48(86.8)	
		<i>Tilapia zilli</i>	10(24.4)	23(56.1)	8(19.5)	
		<i>Tilapia maria</i>	21(30.9)	35(51.5)	12(17.6)	
		<i>Sarotherodon-Galilus</i>	14(22.2)	35(55.6)	14(22.2)	
		<i>Oreochromis-Miloticus</i>	19(37.3)	18(35.3)	14(27.5)	
	Polyteriformes			34(45.9)	19(25.7)	21(28.5)
		<i>Polypteridae</i>		34(5.9)	19(25.7)	21(28.5)
			<i>Polypterus-Senegalus</i>	34(5.9)	19(25.7)	21(28.5)
	Siluriformes	<i>Clariidae</i>		61(121.1)	30(33.3)	28(31.1)
			32(35.5)	30(33.33)	28(31.1)	
		<i>Clarias-Gsariepinus</i>	32(35.5)	30(33.3)	28(31.1)	
<i>Malapteruridae</i>			9(26.5)	18(6.12)	7(20.6)	
			<i>Malapterurus-Electricus</i>	9(26.5)	18(6.12)	7(20.6)
<i>Mochockidae</i>			20(59.1)	19(120.8)	36(82.8)	
			<i>Synodontis-Omias</i>	11(21.6)	10(83.3)	24(53.3)
			<i>Synodontis-Sorex</i>	9(37.5)	9(37.5)	6(24.0)
		TOTAL		326(100) 34.4 %	353(100) 37.2 %	269(100) 28.4 %

4.3 Fish species variation in relation to stations

The percentage abundance of fish in relation to stations table 3 above. A total number of 948 species, composed of 8 order, 14 families and 24 species was recorded in the study. The overall percentage abundance was highest in station B. 37.2 %, followed by station A 34.4 %. And the lowest was station C 28.4 %. *mormyrusune* was more abundance in station B, 44.4 % followed by C (28.9 %) and station A 12 (26.9 %) *Heterotisi-loticus* sp was highest in station A 13 (44.8 %) followed by station B. (34.5 %) and lastly in C (20.7 %).

4.4 Variation of Fish Species in Relation to Seasons

The result of the fish species in relation to seasons revealed that higher abundance of fish species occurred in dry season (50.0 %) followed by wet season 49.4 %. *Districhodus-rustratus* Sp was lowest in wet season 6(31.6) followed by *Epipetatsybi-fasciatus* 8(30.8) in wet season, followed again by *Hepsetusodoe* Sp in dry season 9(39.1) and lately *Heterotisi-anguilloids* 9(31.0) in wet season. Therefore, the higher abundance value was recorded in dry season compared to lower abundance recorded in wet seasons (Table 4).

Table 4: Variation of Fish in Urasi Stram in relation to season July-June 2022-2023

TAXA			SEASONS		
Order	Family	Species	WET	DRY	
Osteoglossi-Forms			41(127.0)	58(117.0)	
	<i>Mormyridae</i>		41(127.0)	58(117.0)	
		<i>Mormyrus-Rume</i>	19(42.2)	36(57.8)	
		<i>Petrocephalus-borei</i>	13(4.8)	16(55.3)	
		<i>Mormyrops-Anguilloides</i>	9(36.0)	16(55.2)	
	<i>Arapaimidae (osteoglossidae)</i>		9(31.0)	20(68.9)	
		<i>Heterotisi-Iniloticus</i>	9(31.0)	20(68.9)	
Anabanti-Forms			12(46.2)	14(53.8)	
	<i>Anabantidae</i>		12(46.2)	14(53.8)	
		<i>Ctenopoma-Kings leyar</i>	12(46.2)	14(53.8)	
Cyprinodon-Tiforms			8(30.8)	18(69.2)	
	<i>Aplocheiidae</i>		8(30.8)	18(69.2)	
			<i>Epiplatys-Fasciatus</i>	8(30.8)	18(69.2)
Characiformes			40(145.4)	69(241.5)	
	<i>Alestidae (Characidae)</i>		13(38.2)	21(61.8)	
			<i>Hydrocynus Forkali</i>	13(38.2)	21(61.8)
			<i>Hydrocynus Vittatus</i>	15(65.2)	16(69.6)
			<i>Brycinuleucicus</i>	12(42.9)	16(69.6)
	<i>Citharinidae</i>		10(27.8)	26(72.2)	
			<i>Citharus-citharinus</i>	10(27.8)	26(72.2)
	<i>Distichodontidae</i>		6(31.6)	13(68.4)	
			<i>Distichodus-Rostratus</i>	6(31.6)	13(68.4)
	Perciformes	<i>Hepsetidae</i>		11(47.8)	9(39.1)
			<i>Hepsetusodoe</i>	11(47.8)	9(39.1)
		<i>Channidae</i>		47(127.7)	66(186.3)
			47(127.7)	66(186.3)	
<i>Parachanna-Obscura</i>			10(33.3)	20(66.7)	
<i>Parachanna-africana</i>			17(50.0)	24(70.6)	
Cichliformes	<i>Cichlidae</i>	<i>Channachanna</i>	20(44.4)	22(49.0)	
			128(230.2)	95(169.6)	
			128(230.2)	95(169.6)	
		<i>Tilapia zilli</i>	26(63.4)	15(36.5)	
	<i>Tilapia maria</i>	38(55.9)	30(44.1)		

	<i>Sarotherodon-Galilus</i>	39(61.9)	24(38.1)
	<i>Oreochromis-Miloticus</i>	25(49.0)	26(50.9)
Polyteriformes		40(54.1)	34(45.9)
	<i>Polypteridae</i>	40(54.1)	34(45.9)
	<i>Polypterus-Senegalus</i>	40(54.1)	34(45.9)
Siluriformes		116(237.7)	80(159.0)
	<i>Clariidae</i>	52(57.8)	55(38.9)
	<i>Clarias-Gsariepinus</i>	52(57.8)	35(38.9)
	<i>Malapteruridae</i>	24(70.6)	10(29.4)
	<i>Malapterurus-Electricus</i>	24(70.6)	10(29.4)
	<i>Mochockidae</i>	40(109.3)	35(90.7)
	<i>Synodontis-Omias</i>	26(51.0)	25(449.0)
	<i>Synodontis-Sorex</i>	14(58.3)	10(41.7)
	TOTAL	468(100) 49.4 %	470(100) 50.0 %

5. CONCLUSIONS

Fish resources are vulnerable to environmental pollution and other human activities and can quickly decay especially when subjected to environmental and human activities simultaneously to decline fish production. This obviously will impact fisheries resources of Urasi Stream. Therefore, periodic evaluation of its fishery resources is important. The knowledge from the study is useful in policy formulation and implementation for the purpose of conserving and boosting fisheries. Many species of carnivorous and larvivorous fishes prey upon insects and their larvae in water. These fishes can be used to control harmful insects, mosquito larvae, etc. *Gambusia affinis* is a well-known fish for mosquito control, hence called mosquito fish. Other larvivorous species are *Brachydanio spp.*, *Rasbora spp.*, *Puntius spp.*, *Esomus spp.*, *Colisa spp.*, *Barilius spp.*, *Chela spp.*, etc. They help in biological control of dengue, malaria, filaria, encephalitis, etc. Similarly, the herbivorous species like grass carp (*Ctenopharyngodon idella*), tilapia (*Oreochromis spp.*), silver barb (*Puntius gonionotus*), etc. are used to control aquatic weed and vegetation.

DECLARATION

The Authors declared no conflict of interest.

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